

Dual Arm Aerial Manipulation while Flying, Holding and Perching: Comparative Case Study

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Abstract. This paper presents a comparative study of three operation modes for an aerial manipulation robot, considering as illustrative application example the realization of maintenance operations on power lines while flying, holding, or perching. Relying in our previous works, and taking into account practical considerations and limitations of the aerial platforms and the manipulators in outdoor scenarios, this paper provides a qualitative and quantitative evaluation and comparison of these three operation modes, identifying some relevant factors that determine the reliability of the system in the realization of the intended task. The paper is mainly focused on lightweight and compliant dual arm manipulators that allow the realization of dexterous and bimanual manipulation tasks on flight, as well as the use of one of the arms for estimating the aerial robot position with respect to a grasping point, or exploiting the kinematic redundancy of the arms to maintain the equilibrium while perching on the power line once deployed in the workspace. The paper also considers the dynamics and control of the aerial manipulator in the usual decoupled scheme, identifying the key terms in the model that determine the behavior of the coupled dynamics according to the particular configuration of the arms when integrated in the aerial platform.

Keywords: Aerial Robotic Manipulation, Dual Arm Manipulation, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, Power Line Maintenance.

1 Introduction

Aerial robotic manipulators [1][2][3] have demonstrated in last decade the possibility to conduct different tasks involving physical interaction on flight with objects or the environment, extending the range of operations of multirotor platforms [4] through the integration of grippers, robotic arms, and other tools. The widespread interest in the development of this kind of robots is motivated by the necessity to conduct diverse inspection and maintenance tasks in high altitude workspaces such as power lines [5], pipelines in chemical plants [6], bridges [7][8], and other infrastructures [9][10]. In the design and development of this kind of robots, it is possible to identify three different approaches depending on which is the main constrain or criteria to satisfy [1], either the payload capacity, maximum size or weight of the overall robot, or required level of dexterity imposed by the task. Simple contact-based inspection tasks [8][9][11] can be

accomplished integrating single link manipulators providing a certain level of accommodation at the end effector, relying on the force/impedance control capabilities of the multirotor platform to exert the contact force. Specific benchmarks for evaluating the performance of the aerial robot were proposed in [12]. Alternatively, other simulation [13] and experimental [14][15][16] works propose the use of dual arm aerial robots to conduct tasks involving dexterous manipulation with interaction force control. Dual arm [17] and even three arm [18] aerial manipulation has been proposed for valve turning and object grasping tasks, although the position control of the servo actuators employed in these works involve a stiff interaction with the manipulated object. In order to prevent the rigid propagation of the wrenches from the end effector to the multirotor base while protecting the actuators from impacts and overloads and facilitating the accommodation of the aerial manipulator to unavoidable position deviations, references [14][15][16] exploited the mechanical joint compliance with visual [14] or joint [15][16] deflection measurement to control the contact forces and achieve desired impedance behavior. The anthropomorphic design of the arms described in [14][15] allows the realization of complex bimanual manipulation tasks like the installation of helical bird flight diverters on power lines [5], operation intended for human workers, whereas [16] explores the use of one arm for grabbing the power line so the position of the aerial robot relative to the grabbing point can be easily obtained from the end effector position. Reference [15] also compares two configurations of aerial manipulators (standard and long reach, assimilated to cable suspended [19][20]) in terms of safety due to the risk of collision of the propellers with the environmental obstacles.

Although most works in this field assumed that the aerial manipulation task is carried out on flight, the convenience to improve the end effector positioning accuracy and increase the operation time (typically limited by the multirotor platform) has led to the development of hybrid aerial-rolling robots [21][22] capable to land and move along the workspace. However, the integration of mobile bases tends to increase significantly the overall weight since these should be robust and powerful enough to carry the aerial robot. Thus, the aerial transportation and deployment [23] of the manipulation robot can be a more suitable solution.

Fig. 1. Dual arm aerial manipulation while flying (left), holding (middle), and perching (right).

The main contribution of this paper is to present a qualitative and quantitative evaluation and comparison of three operation modes of aerial manipulation robots, as shown in **Fig. 1**: flying, holding, and perching. Based on our previous works in this field [14][15][16][22], and considering the realization of maintenance operations on power lines as illustrative use case [5], the paper identifies which are the main factors affecting the aerial robot performance in terms of metrics like positioning accuracy, force generation capacity, or operation time [12]. Experimental results are presented, using the LiCAS A1 anthropomorphic dual arm manipulator [24] integrated in a medium scale quadrotor.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the notation and preliminaries in the modeling and control of the aerial manipulator. Section 3 is focused on the aerial manipulation while flying, whereas Section 4 considers the manipulation while holding, and Section 5 is devoted to the aerial manipulation in perching conditions. Finally, Section 6 provides some conclusions derived from the comparison of the three operation modes.

2 Modeling, Control and Characterization

2.1 System Modeling

In the definition of the task, three reference frames are considered [12][14][15][16]: the Earth fixed frame $\{\mathbf{E}\}$, typically associated to the take-off position, the multirotor base frame $\{\mathbf{B}\}$, and the manipulator frame $\{\mathbf{i}\}$, with $i = \{1, 2\}$ indicating the arm index (left/right). For convenience, we also define the reference frame $\{\mathbf{0}\}$ at the midpoint of $\{\mathbf{1}\}$ and $\{\mathbf{2}\}$. The multirotor position in the inertial frame is denoted as $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{B}}^{\mathbf{E}} = [x, y, z]^T$, and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\mathbf{B}}^{\mathbf{E}} = [\phi, \theta, \psi]^T$ is the orientation expressed in the Euler angles roll, pitch and yaw. Considering a flexible joint dual arm manipulator, the rotation angle of the j -th servo of the i -th arm will be denoted as θ_j^i , whereas q_j^i is the corresponding output link angle. The difference between them is the deflection angle $\Delta\theta_j^i = \theta_j^i - q_j^i$ caused by the compression of the springs in the flexible joints [14]. Each of the arms provides N joints for end effector positioning ($N = 4$ in [14][15], and $N = 3$ in [16]). Therefore, the corresponding joint position vectors $\boldsymbol{\theta}^i \in \mathfrak{R}^N$ and $\mathbf{q}^i \in \mathfrak{R}^N$ are defined for each arm. Denoting by \mathbf{r}_{TCPi}^i the tool center point (TCP) position of the i -th arm in its own frame, then the forward and inverse kinematic models are defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{r}_{TCPi}^i = \mathbf{FK}^i(\mathbf{q}^i) \ ; \ \mathbf{q}^i = \mathbf{IK}^i(\mathbf{r}_{TCPi}^i, \varphi_i) \quad (1)$$

where φ_i is a parameter, which is necessary to solve the $\mathfrak{R}^N \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}^3$ mapping in case of redundant manipulators ($N > 3$). In order to account for the different possible configurations of the manipulator when integrated on the multirotor base (standard, long reach or cable suspended [15][19]), we characterize the position displacement and rotation of the dual arm frame $\{\mathbf{0}\}$ with respect to $\{\mathbf{B}\}$ as a function of the variables $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\mathbf{0}}^{\mathbf{B}} =$

$[\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \varepsilon_z]$ and $\Delta\boldsymbol{\eta}_0^B = [\phi_0^B, \theta_0^B, \psi_0^B]$, which are the roll, pitch and yaw angles that define the rotation from $\{\mathbf{0}\}$ to $\{\mathbf{B}\}$.

Considering the Euler-Lagrange formulation, the aerial manipulator dynamics can be derived from the Lagrangian and the generalized equations of the forces:

$$\mathbf{q} = [\mathbf{r}_B^E \quad \boldsymbol{\eta}_B^E \quad \boldsymbol{\theta}^1 \quad \boldsymbol{\theta}^2 \quad \mathbf{q}^1 \quad \mathbf{q}^2 \quad \Delta\varepsilon_0^B \quad \Delta\boldsymbol{\eta}_0^B] \quad (2)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Gamma} = [\mathbf{F}_B^E \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_B^E \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_s^1 \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_s^2 \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}^1 \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}^2 \quad \mathbf{F}_0^B \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_0^B] \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{F}_B^E and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_B^E$ are forces and moments acting on the multirotor base, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_s^i$ are $\boldsymbol{\tau}^i$ the servo and output link torques in the compliant joints, whereas \mathbf{F}_0^B and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_0^B$ are the forces and torques acting on the manipulator base that tend to cause a position and orientation deviation with respect to the multirotor base. These wrenches do not apply when the arms are rigidly attached to the multirotor base, but they should be considered in the long reach [15] or cable suspended configurations [25] (see Section 3). Depending on how the manipulator is attached to the multirotor base, the time derivatives of some coordinates of $\Delta\mathbf{r}_0^B$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_0^B$ will be zero, so these can be removed from the dynamic model.

The equations of motion of the aerial manipulator can therefore be derived from the Lagrangian L , defined as the difference between the kinetic and potential energies, K and V , respectively, following the Euler-Lagrange approach:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left\{ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{q}}} \right\} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{q}} = \boldsymbol{\Gamma} + \boldsymbol{\Gamma}_{\text{ext}} \quad ; \quad L = K - V \quad (4)$$

Here $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_{\text{ext}}$ represents the external wrenches exerted on the aerial manipulator due to the interaction with the environment. The kinetic and potential energies are computed from the position of the masses of the aerial manipulator expressed in the inertial frame, considering the gravity and the elastic potential stored in the compliant joints [14] in the computation of the potential energy. The dynamic model can be expressed in the usual matrix form:

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q})\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{C}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}, \mathbf{q})\dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{D}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}) = \boldsymbol{\Gamma} + \boldsymbol{\Gamma}_{\text{ext}} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{G} , \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{D} are the inertia, centrifugal/Coriolis, gravity, stiffness and damping terms, respectively. Note that the dimension of these matrices and vectors depends on the number of joints of the arms and the number of joints that characterize the mechanical coupling of the manipulator on the multirotor base. A qualitative analysis is provided in Subsection 2.3 regarding the dynamic coupling between manipulator and multirotor depending on the particular integration configuration.

2.2 Control Scheme

Most multi-rotor flight controllers widely used nowadays, like the Pixhawk, DJI A3 or CUAV, as well as open-source software like PX4 [26], do not consider the effect of

interaction wrenches [27] due to the dynamic coupling with the manipulator, or the external wrenches due to contact forces, but these hardware and software implementations are intended for the control of multirotor platforms in free and unconstrained flight. Then we adopt a decoupled control scheme [1] in which the quadrotor platform considers the dynamic coupling as a perturbation. This is represented in **Fig. 2**. The multirotor implements a cascade controller [28] that takes as input the position or velocity reference in the inertial frame, giving as output an attitude reference that is fed to the attitude controller, that at the same time gives as output an angular rate reference provided to the corresponding controller that generates the appropriate control signals for the roll (U_1), pitch (U_2) and yaw (U_3) angles. The altitude controller is in this case a PID that takes as input the velocity reference and provides the mean thrust of the rotors, U_4 .

A task-oriented control scheme is proposed for the dual arm manipulator, as depicted in **Fig. 2**. The core component is the Task Manager [15], a functional block that implements the different manipulation operations of the arms, consisting typically in executing a trajectory or sequence of motion primitives, involving in some cases the control of the contact forces relying on the mechanical joint compliance with visual [14] or joint [15][16] deflection measurement. This scheme relies on the forward/inverse kinematics, or Jacobian based methods, for generating the appropriate joint references sent to the arms servos, exploiting the feedback provided by smart actuators to obtain the current end effector position, velocity or a torque estimation based on the pulse width modulation (PWM) signal generated by the servo controller [12].

Fig. 2. Decoupled control scheme of the dual arm aerial manipulator. Velocity-attitude-rate cascade multirotor controller (up), task-oriented controller of the arms relying on servo controller (down). The dynamic coupling occurs physically between the arms and the multirotor. For space reasons, only the X-axis velocity/attitude (pitch) control is represented.

2.3 Effect of Manipulator Configuration on Flight Controller

The dynamic coupling between the manipulator and the multirotor identified in **Fig. 2** and associated to the crossed terms in the inertia, Coriolis and gravity components in Equation (4), may cause qualitatively different behaviors depending on:

- The configuration of the manipulator when integrated in the multirotor platform: (1) standard, in which the arms are rigidly attached at the multirotor base [14][16], (2) long reach, also known as passive pendulum [15], or (3) cable suspended [25].
- The operation mode: flying [15], holding with one arm while the other conducts the operation [16], or perching/landed so there is no dynamic coupling on flight [22].

The embedded position controller and the relatively high friction of the servo actuators integrated in the joints make possible to assume that the dynamic coupling in terms of inertia and Coriolis from the multirotor to the robotic arms can be neglected, whereas the effect of the arms motion over the multirotor may be noticeable, particularly when the arms are moving a load and the inertia becomes much more significant. This has motivated the interest in the design and development of several prototypes of light-weight manipulators [1]. The specific benchmarking procedures and metrics for aerial manipulators described in [12] will be taken into account in next sections.

3 Aerial Manipulation while Flying

Literature review on aerial robotic manipulation [1] evidences that most research works assume that the intended operation (object grasping, pick-and-place, wall pushing...) is conducted on flight. In this sense, the aerial platform serves as mobile base for the robotic manipulator, supporting the reaction wrenches generated by the motion of the arms or the external wrenches that disturb the attitude controller and induce a position deviation that affects the end effector positioning accuracy. The multirotor position controller benchmark test described in [12] evaluates the position deviation of the aerial platform when the attached manipulator (integrated in standard configuration) lifts a load. We apply here the same evaluation procedure with a novel aerial manipulator configuration denoted as 4-Cable Suspended (4-CS) configuration (also known as “puppet”) in which the shoulder structure of the dual arm is suspended from four cables attached to the multirotor base. This configuration enhances safety by increasing the separation distance between the manipulator and the propellers to reduce the risk of collision during the realization of manipulation tasks like the installation of bird flight diverters on power lines [5]. The use of four cables instead of two as in [25] is motivated by the convenience to avoid the counter-rotation in pitch of the shoulder base when the arms lift a load, so the 4-CS prevents the roll-pitch rotations, resulting in a horizontal position deviation. This corresponds to the term $\Delta\epsilon_0^B$ in Equation (2), where $\epsilon_z \cong 0$, and the only relative orientation angle of $\{0\}$ w.r.t. $\{B\}$ is in yaw, whereas $\phi_0^B \cong 0$, $\theta_0^B \cong 0$ (see the definition of $\Delta\eta_0^B$ above Equation (2)).

The experiment represented in **Fig. 3** and **Fig. 4** illustrates the effect of the dynamic coupling and the passive dynamics associated to the displacement term $\Delta\epsilon_0^B$ in Equation

(2) when the arms lift an helical bird flight diverter (a device typically employed on the Spanish power grid to prevent the collision of the birds with the cables) rotating the elbow and shoulder joints consecutively. As it can be seen, the pitch moment exerted on the shoulder base when the device (0.6 kg) is lifted, is transmitted to the multirotor by the pair of strings, causing a position deviation $\varepsilon_B^E \approx 0.15 \text{ m}$ on the base, and $\varepsilon_0^B \approx 0.2 \text{ m}$ on the shoulder structure w.r.t. the multirotor. The deviation is much more evident when the device is lifted by rotating the shoulder joint, such that $\varepsilon_B^E \approx 0.3 \text{ m}$ and $\varepsilon_0^B \approx 0.5 \text{ m}$. Note that the reach of the arm is 0.5 m , so the magnitude of the errors will difficult the realization of the task. The passive coupling of the 4-CS also reduces the ability to exert pushing/pulling forces in the forward and lateral direction. Finally, **Fig. 4** evidences the relatively fast attenuation of the oscillations due to the damping.

Fig. 3. Position deviation of a 4-cable suspended configuration dual arm aerial manipulator due to the motion of the elbow and shoulder joints while grabbing a helical device (0.6 kg weight).

Fig. 4. Experimental results of the multirotor and dual arm position deviations. The position deviation of the multirotor and manipulator is more evident with the shoulder rotation (60 deg).

4 Aerial Manipulation while Holding

One of the main challenges in the practical application of aerial manipulation robots is the accurate position control in outdoor environments. Consider again as illustrative example the installation of bird flight diverters on power lines [5], involving accuracies in the range of a few centimeters imposed by the dimensions and installation procedure of these devices. Although significant advances have been achieved in simultaneous localization and mapping [29], the weight of cameras and LIDAR (light detection and ranging) sensors, along with the computational resources required to obtain the position estimation, tends to increase the overall weight, size and complexity of the aerial robot.

The dual arm aerial manipulation robot presented in [16] is intended to conduct the manipulation task with one arm (operation arm) while the other one (holding arm) is grabbed to a fixed point in a power line, exploiting the joint position measurements of the servo actuators in the elbow and shoulder joints to estimate the position of the aerial platform relative to the grabbing point. This is represented in **Fig. 5** and **Fig. 6**. Note that the estimation error, using an Opti-Track system as ground truth, is under 20 mm, but it increases up to 50 [mm] when the multirotor rotates in yaw (Y-axis deviation) as the holding arm does not incorporate wrist joints that allow the accommodation of the arm to deviations in this axis. Although not explored in [16] a dual arm system allows the realization of manipulation tasks in closed kinematic chains [30], in such a way that the forces exerted by the operation arm can be partially supported by the holding arm, exploiting the mechanical compliance to achieve desired impedance behavior [14][16].

Fig. 5. Dual arm aerial manipulator grabbed with the right arm to a linear infrastructure.

Fig. 6. Multirotor displacement flying while grabbed with right arm (left). Error the position estimation obtained from the grabbing arm, and multirotor yaw (right).

5 Aerial Manipulation while Perching

A new concept that has not been explored is the aerial transportation and deployment of the manipulator on the workspace, detaching the arms from the multirotor platform to facilitate the perching. **Fig. 7** illustrates this idea in a power line testbed operation in which the arms are used to install clip-type bird flight diverters [5], incorporating a rolling base to move along the line. This new configuration also allows to perch since the center of mass of the manipulator is below the contact point of the rolling base, which could not be done if the multirotor was above. The main benefits are twofold. On the one hand, higher positioning accuracy at end effector can be achieved since there is no dynamic coupling with the aerial platform during the manipulation task. The operation depicted in **Fig. 7** requires position errors below 10 mm to install the clamp mechanism since the separation of the clamp is 25 mm . On the other hand, this configuration is more energy efficient compared to [22], where the hybrid aerial-rolling robot has to carry the weight of the entire platform. During the aerial transportation, the arms are suspended from a hook-handle mechanism that induces a negligible moment in pitch (θ_0^B in Equation (2)). However, an under-actuated dynamics is raised in the roll angle of the manipulator base when perched.

Fig. 7. Approaching (A1), detachment (A2) and deployment (A3) of dual arm manipulator with rolling base on power line. Installation of clip-type bird flight diverter: rest pose (B1), device grasping (B2), approaching device with left arm on power line (B3), and installation (B4).

The evolution of the signals of interest during the realization of previous experiment (**Fig. 7**) are shown in **Fig. 8**. It is interesting to realize that, when the dual arm system is detached from the multirotor, the aerial platform experiences a sudden loss of 3.2 kg payload, resulting in a momentarily vertical climbing (see **Fig. 7–A3**) since the flight controller is commanded in that instant to maintain a zero velocity (see the PID Climb Rate Controller in **Fig. 2**). **Fig. 8** also represents the trajectory followed by the TCP (tool center point) of the left arm during the installation of the bird flight diverter.

Fig. 8. Multirotor thrust and altitude during the dual arm deployment on the power line (left). Left arm TCP position during the installation of the bird diverter (right): grasping (1) and retrieval (2), positioning around the power line (3) and impulsive movement for installing (4).

6 Conclusion

This paper presented a comparative study of three aerial manipulation operation modes: flying, holding, and perching. Significant position deviations of the dual arm w.r.t. the multirotor base were identified in the 4-Cable Suspended configuration due to the reaction wrenches generated when the arms lift a load, requiring appropriate coordinated control of both parts to conduct the task. Relatively accurate position estimations can be obtained in the holding configuration in which one arm is grabbed to a fixed point in the environment, imposing desired impedance behavior on this arm to facilitate the accommodation of the multirotor during the realization of the task. Finally, the paper also described the aerial transportation and deployment of a dual arm manipulator on a power line, removing in this way the inconveniences of the aerial platform in terms of dynamic coupling, limited flight time, and positioning accuracy.

The practical application of aerial manipulators in real outdoor scenarios like power lines, pipelines, viaducts, and other high altitude infrastructures requires the accurate localization and control of the robot relative to the workspace such that the position deviations of the aerial platform are approximately lower than the 10% of the effective reach of the manipulator. In this sense, the combination of LIDAR with visual-inertial odometry methods seem to be the most suitable solution, as long as the size and weight of these components are compatible with the aerial manipulation robot. Conventional autopilots like Pixhawk and flight control software like PX4 or Ardupilot should be upgraded to support the physical interactions raised on flight during the realization of manipulation tasks, or the adaptation to mass variations in the aerial deployment or retrieval of the robotic manipulator.

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